

Evolution of bismuth oxide catalysts during electrochemical CO₂ reduction

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ABSTRACT

Bismuth is a promising electrocatalyst for active and selective CO₂ electroreduction to formate. Herein, we investigated the evolution of various Bi-based catalysts (β -Bi₂O₃ nanoparticles, BiOBr nanosheets, Bi₂O₂CO₃ nanosheets, and large α -Bi₂O₃ and β -Bi₂O₃ particles) during reaction. Apart from the α -Bi₂O₃ particles, all the electrocatalysts reach the same Faradaic efficiency ($93 \pm 2\%$) and current density during potentiostatic operation, and their morphology changed to nanosheets. This change in morphology can be linked to the formation of Bi₂O₂CO₃ layers, which are prone to reduction to metallic Bi. The final phase and morphology depend on the size of the Bi precursor. Quasi-in situ XPS suggests that a Bi₂O₂CO₃ contribution persists on the surface even for the reduced catalysts. At a current density of 200 mA/cm², all catalysts reduce to metallic Bi without forming a well-defined sheet morphology. Only for the Bi₂O₃ nanoparticles can a FE above 90% be maintained.

1. Introduction

Replacing fossil resources with CO₂ as a carbon source to produce chemicals and energy carriers is a promising way to decrease anthropogenic CO₂ emissions [1]. Electrochemical conversion of CO₂ offers a direct way of using renewable electricity to produce energy-dense fuels and intermediate chemicals. Several products can be obtained by CO₂ electroreduction (CO₂ER), including C₁ products such as CO, methane, methanol, and formic acid, as well as products with C-C bonds such as ethylene, ethanol, and propanol [2]. One of the most straightforward reduction products of CO₂ is formic acid, as the reduction mechanism from CO₂ to formate requires only two electrons. The relatively high market value compared to the other CO₂ reduction products and low electron demand make it one of the most promising products for early adoption and commercialization of CO₂ER [3,4]. The current demand for formic acid in the feed industry and leather tanning is covered by hydrolysis of methyl formate with an annual production capacity of ca. 0.8 Mtonne [5]. Additionally, formic acid has the potential to serve as a liquid hydrogen carrier for on-demand energy storage and reuse [3,6]. Several metals (Sn, Bi, In, and Pb) have been identified as promising catalysts for CO₂ electroreduction to formate and formic acid [2,3,7]. Among these, Bi catalysts are reported to reach the highest Faradaic efficiencies (FEs) close to 100% at the lowest overpotential [3,7–9]. To optimize performance, Bi-based catalysts have been synthesized in a

wide variety of morphologies and phases [3]. Commonly, a phase change is observed upon electrochemical reduction of the as-prepared catalyst, leading to metallic Bi, Bi₂O₃ or Bi₂O₂CO₃ [9–13]. Vivier and coworkers described in detail the reduction mechanisms of Bi₂O₃ and Bi₂O₂CO₃, showing that the reduction mechanism can proceed via the dissolution of BiO₂ ions in alkaline media [14,15]. These observations demonstrate that the initial morphology is not necessarily relevant to electrochemical CO₂ reduction. Specifically, nanosheet morphologies have received significant attention in electrocatalysis and photocatalysis [8,9,16–18]. They are obtained by intercalating a halide (X) between Bi₂O₂²⁺ layers, forming Bi-oxyhalide (BiOX) crystal phases [8,9,19–21]. Detailed characterization of the nanosheets and quantum-chemical calculations suggest an effect of the enhanced local electric field of the thin sheet morphology to explain the improved electrocatalytic performance [11,22–24]. It has also been found that other Bi-containing materials transform into sheet-like morphologies during electrochemical reactions [10,11,25].

Therefore, it is crucial to further investigate the transformation of Bi-containing catalysts during or after (prolonged) CO₂ER. Broekmann and coworkers recently reported how experimental conditions during CO₂ER impact the morphology of Bi₂O₃ dendrites and its FE towards formate [10,26]. Their work highlights the necessity to characterize the Bi catalyst at high current densities without CO₂ mass transport limitations, better representing the practical conditions of electrochemical

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formate synthesis. Their findings show that the initial dendritic shape of Bi oxide changed into sheets after the reaction. Additionally, they showed that the Bi₂O₂CO₃ phase can be stabilized by a high local concentration of CO₂, even at high current densities. The formed Bi₂O₂CO₃ exhibits higher FE compared to Bi₂O₃ and metallic Bi. Despite this important study, how the initial morphology impacts the evolution of the active phase and the electrocatalytic activity remains to be seen. Such understanding could help the practical implementation of Bi catalysts for electrochemical CO₂ reduction [27–29].

In this work, we investigated the evolution of the morphology and chemical state of various Bi-containing catalysts during CO₂ER. As catalyst precursors, we employed Bi₂O₃ nanoparticles prepared by flame spray pyrolysis (FSP), Bi₂O₃CO₃, BiOBr, and commercially obtained Bi₂O₃. FSP is a versatile one-step synthesis technique for preparing nanometer-sized catalysts with a narrow size distribution [30–32]. Although FSP is used here to obtain small amounts of well-defined catalysts, it can also be scaled up to obtain quantities relevant to the industrial scale [33–35]. Despite the versatility of FSP, this method has yet to be widely explored to synthesize catalysts for CO₂ electroreduction [36,37]. BiOBr nanosheets are synthesized by a hydrothermal method, while Bi₂O₃CO₃ is obtained by prolonged exposure of Bi₂O₃ in the air. The catalysts are characterized by electrochemical methods, and the electrocatalytic performance is studied at industrially relevant current densities for prolonged times using a gas diffusion electrode configuration. XRD, XPS, and SEM are employed to reveal the changes in the catalyst phase and morphology and its effect on the catalyst activity. This work provides a systematic comparison of different precursors, in a wide range of experimental conditions. This comparison allows us to determine how parameters such as initial size and phase influence the FE after structural transformations that are common for Bi-based catalysts.

2. Methods

2.1. Catalyst preparation

2.1.1. Bi₂O₃ nanoparticles

Nanoparticles (NP) of Bi₂O₃ are prepared by a one-step flame spray pyrolysis (FSP) method using a Tethis NPS10 setup. A 0.15 M Bi(NO₃)₃•5 H₂O (99%, Alfa Aesar) precursor solution is prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts in a solvent mixture of ethanol (99.9%, Biosolve) and 2-ethylhexanoic acid (99%, Sigma-Aldrich) in equal volume ratio. The solution was acidified using nitric acid (65%, Merck) until a clear solution required approximately 10 v% nitric acid. The solution was then injected into the nozzle of the flame synthesis setup. The flame was fed with a flow of 3.0 L/min O₂ and 1.5 L/min CH₄, adding a dispersion flow of 5.0 L/min O₂. The solid particles were collected from a quartz filter placed downstream of the flame region. Bi₂O₃ nanoparticles with an average size of around 20 nm were prepared by FSP, filtered through a 250 μm steel sieve, and labeled Bi₂O₃-NP. Bi₂O₃ powders were obtained commercially with an average particle size of 200 nm (Alfa Aesar), labeled Bi₂O₃-C1, and 10 μm (Sigma Aldrich), labeled Bi₂O₃-C2. The as-prepared Bi₂O₃ catalyst was stored in an N₂ atmosphere. After electrode preparation, the experiments are performed within days after preparation to ensure the original Bi₂O₃ starting phase.

2.1.2. BiOBr nanosheets

BiOBr nanosheets (BiOBr-NS) were synthesized using a modified protocol from Xia et al. [19]. In a typical synthesis, 970 mg Bi(NO₃)₃•5 H₂O and 500 mg CTAB (Merck) were dissolved in 50 ml ultrapure water (18.2 MΩ/cm, Elga Purelab flex). Then, 3 g urea was added to 10 ml ultrapure water and 40 ml ethanol absolute (dry, Merck) to obtain a homogeneous solution by stirring. Next, the urea solution was added to the Bi(NO₃)₃ solution, and the resulting mixture was stirred for 30 min, which resulted in a white homogeneous suspension. In an oil bath, this suspension was refluxed for 4 h at 90 °C. The resulting BiOBr nanosheets were collected by centrifugation, washed with ultrapure water and

ethanol absolute, and dried at 60 °C.

2.1.3. Bi₂O₂CO₃ sheets

The Bi₂O₂CO₃ sheets (BOC-NS) are obtained by air exposure of the Bi₂O₃-NP until complete conversion is obtained. The needed duration for air exposure depends on the batch size and exposed surface. A gram sized batch in a 20 ml vial of the Bi₂O₃-NP was fully converted to Bi₂O₂CO₃ sheets 6 months after synthesis.

2.1.4. Gas diffusion electrode (GDE) preparation

A catalyst suspension was prepared by weighing appropriate amounts of Bi catalyst and dispersing the particles by sonication in 3 ml isopropanol (99.9%, Sigma-Aldrich) and 1 ml ultrapure water. Nafion ionomer solution (D-520, dispersion, 5% w/w in water and isopropanol, Alfa Aesar) was added to reach a 20 wt% Nafion-to-catalyst ratio. The solution was sonicated for ~30 min to ensure a good dispersion. The ink was sprayed with a spray gun on a commercial gas diffusion layer (ELAT LT1400W, FuelCellStore). The loading was determined by weighing the GDL before and the GDE after catalyst deposition and amounted to 0.36 ± 0.12 mg/cm².

2.2. Characterization

2.2.1. X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS)

XPS was performed with a K-Alpha XPS apparatus (Thermo Scientific) using an aluminum anode (Kα monochromatic irradiation, 1486.6 eV) operating at 72 W and a spot size of 400 μm. High-resolution core level spectra were measured with a pass energy of 50 eV, and wide-range survey spectra were recorded at 200 eV pass energy. The background pressure inside the analysis chamber was kept below 8·10⁻⁸ mbar, reaching a maximum of 3·10⁻⁷ mbar during the measurements due to the flow of low energy Ar⁺ ions for charge neutralization. The spectra were analyzed using CasaXPS software, and energy referencing was performed against the C 1 s peak of adventitious carbon set at a binding energy of 284.5 eV. In case energy referencing with the C 1 s peak was unambiguous and a presence of metallic Bi was observed, the Bi 4 f binding energy was set at 156.9 eV, [38] assuming that the metal peak does not show a shift caused by charging due to the high conductivity of metallic Bi. The peaks were deconvoluted using a Shirley background and GL(30) line shape. The metallic Bi peak was fitted using an LA(1, 1.02,175) line shape obtained from a Bi reference sample, etched under an ultrahigh vacuum inside the XPS apparatus (Fig. S12).

2.2.2. Quasi in situ X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

Quasi-in situ XPS was performed using a SPECS Phoibos NAP-150 electron analyzer. The core-line spectra were acquired using a monochromatic aluminum anode (Kα=1486.6 eV, SPECS XR-50) operated at 50 W. The pass energy was set to 40 eV with a step size of 0.1 eV and a dwell time of 0.5 s. No charge neutralization could be utilized during XPS analysis. The electrochemical measurements were performed in the featured three-electrode electrochemical cell (SPECS, IS-EC-AP) using a Pt wire as a counter electrode and an Ag/AgCl reference electrode (Redox.me, measured at 0.23 V vs SHE at pH 1). The electrolyte, 0.5 M KHCO₃, was purged with N₂ gas and subsequently saturated with CO₂ before the start of the measurement. During the measurements, CO₂ gas bubbled inside the electrochemical cell, and He gas in the chamber where the cell is located. After the size, the electrode stage was released from the cell, transferred for analysis from the inert gas chamber to the ultra-high vacuum system via a buffer chamber without any contact with air, and analyzed for surface compositional changes.

2.2.3. X-ray diffraction (XRD)

XRD was performed using a Bruker D2 Phaser diffractometer with Cu Kα radiation (1.5406 Å). The XRD diffractograms were recorded between 2θ = 10° and 90° at 1 s/step scan rate and a step size of 0.02°. XRD of catalyst powder and catalyst on the GDEs could be obtained. On the

GDEs, the crystalline PTFE peak was used as a reference at $2\theta = 18^\circ$ [39]. The particle crystalline size was calculated using the Scherrer equation in the DIFFRAC.EVA software package.

2.2.4. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

The particle size of the catalysts was determined using an FEI Tecnai (type Sphera) instrument operating at an acceleration voltage of 200 kV and an FEI cryoTITAN instrument operating at an acceleration voltage of 300 kV. Catalyst particles were dispersed in ethanol via ultrasonication and deposited on a holey Cu grid. Sizes were obtained using the software ImageJ.

2.2.5. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

SEM images were obtained with a CMEM Quanta 30FEG operated at 20–30 kV and magnification up to 120,000x. A backscatter detector increased the contrast between metallic and carbon compounds on the samples.

2.3. Electrochemical characterization

2.3.1. Electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction

CO₂ electroreduction was performed at room temperature in a flow cell with a 1 cm² area electrode (Micro Flow Cell, ElectroCell) in flow-through mode (Fig. S3). A Nafion proton exchange membrane (N324, Ion Power) separates the catholyte and anolyte chambers. The Nafion membrane was pre-treated in a hot 10 v% H₂O₂ (33%, VWR Chemicals) solution (80 °C, 1 h) and subsequently in a hot 3 M H₂SO₄ (≥95%, Merck) solution (80 °C, 1 h). An Autolab 302 N potentiostat was used to record the electrochemical response. A three-electrode system was used with a platinum mesh as a counter electrode and a leakless Ag/AgCl reference electrode (1.6 mm, EDAQ, measured at 0.37 V vs SHE at pH 1). The as-prepared GDEs were used as working electrodes. Potentials are specified against the Ag/AgCl reference electrode. As catholyte, 0.5 M KHCO₃ solution was prepared by weighing high purity KHCO₃ (analysis grade, Merck) and dissolving in ultrapure water. A highly alkaline electrolyte such as KOH would suppress the hydrogen evolution reaction, enabling higher partial current densities towards formate. Nevertheless, it is also known that upon saturation with CO₂, KOH reacts with CO₂ to form KHCO₃. During prolonged CO₂ reduction, the conversion of KOH to KHCO₃ is inevitable. The present work aims at comparing catalysts at conditions that are relevant to continuous CO₂ reduction for industrial applications. Therefore, we chose to start with the 0.5 M KHCO₃ electrolyte. As anolyte, 0.5 M H₂SO₄ solution was used by diluting H₂SO₄ (>95%, Sigma-Aldrich) in ultrapure water. The catholyte solution was degassed by N₂ and saturated with CO₂ before use. The backside of the GDE was supplied with 10 ml/min CO₂. The catholyte and anolyte flow was set at 50 ml/min. Cyclic voltammetry was performed from – 0.1 V to – 2.2 V vs Ag/AgCl, and potentiostatic measurements at potentials down to – 2.2 V vs Ag/AgCl for 30 min. Galvanostatic measurements lasted 6 h at a current density of 200 mA/cm² after which the catholyte was analyzed for products. Faradaic efficiencies towards formate were calculated from the charge ratio needed to produce the obtained formate over the total charge consumed at the cathode, according to Eq. 1.

$$FE = \frac{[FA] * V * n * F}{\int J dt} \quad (1)$$

with [FA] being the concentration of formate in the cathode compartment, V the catholyte volume, n the consumed electrons (two) per formate molecule, F Faraday's constant, J the current density and t time. The experiments were repeated at least 2 times with a fresh GDE having the same loading to calculate the error. The current densities are not corrected for the electrochemically active surface area due to the absence of a non-faradaic region between oxidation and reduction of the catalysts (Fig. S8). Because the surface area changes continuously with

the rapid morphological changes of the catalysts during CO₂ER (Fig. 4), the double-layer capacitance of the gas diffusion electrodes depends on the degree of GDE wetting and cannot be determined reliably [40].

2.4. Product analysis

Dissolved reduction products were analyzed by high-pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC) and 1 H nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (¹H NMR). A Shimadzu HPLC containing a Polar C18 column (Luna® Omega 3 μm, 150 × 3.0 mm) was used to determine the formic acid concentration. The HPLC was run using a potassium phosphate buffer (pH 2.0) as eluent, which was prepared by dissolving 1.4150 g KH₂PO₄ (≥99%, Sigma-Aldrich) and 1.6854 g H₃PO₄ solution (85%, Merck) in 1.0 L ultrapure water. The column oven temperature was set at 30 °C to circumvent the effects of room temperature fluctuations, and the UV-vis detector cell temperature was set at 40 °C. Samples were taken from the catholyte by diluting 100 μL of electrolyte to 1.0 ml with 900 μL 0.1 M H₃PO₄ solution (1:10) to convert bicarbonate to CO₂. An injection volume of 10 μL and a total eluent flow of 500 μL/min was used. The retention time of the FA peak was 1.8 min. Reference solutions from 263.434 mM down to 5.268 mM formic acid (≥ 98%, Sigma-Aldrich) were used for a calibration curve for HPLC analysis. Two stock FA solutions (263.434 mM and 105.60 mM) were prepared by diluting 1.000 ml FA to 100.00 ml and 250 ml in 0.5 M KHCO₃ in ultrapure water and were further diluted for reference solutions. The calibration solutions were also prepared by 1:10 dilution in 0.1 M H₃PO₄ (85%, Merck) and analyzed in triplicate. Peak integrations were performed using the ICIS algorithm included in the Shimadzu software package.

NMR spectra were recorded with a 400 MHz Bruker spectrometer. 450 μL of the solution was taken directly from the catholyte, and 50 μL of D₂O (99.9%, Sigma-Aldrich) was added containing 10 mM DMSO (>99.9%, Biosolve) and 50 mM phenol (≥99%, Sigma-Aldrich) as internal standards. Standard solutions made for HPLC calibration were used to verify the DMSO and phenol concentrations. A solvent pre-saturation sequence reduced the water signal. The signal-to-noise ratio was improved using 48 scans with a 16 s delay time. The resulting spectra were calibrated concerning the DMSO peak position, set at 2.600 ppm in accordance with Kuhl et al. [41]. Then, the peak belonging to the carbon-bonded proton in formic acid was observed at 8.33 ppm.

Gaseous products were analyzed online using a TRACE 1300 gas chromatograph (Thermo Fisher). The permanent gases (H₂, CO, CO₂) and the hydrocarbons (methane, ethylene) were analyzed on separate channels. A Hayesep Q pre-column and a Shin-Carbon ST column with TCD were used for permanent gas analysis. An Al₂O₃/KCl column with FID was used to separate the light hydrocarbons.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Catalyst characterization

FSP was used to obtain Bi₂O₃ nanoparticles (Bi₂O₃-NP). Based on TEM (Fig. 1a), the average particle size is 23 ± 4.6 nm. The particles are spherical in shape and agglomerated. Two Bi₂O₃ particulate samples obtained from a commercial source comprise particles with dimensions of 175 ± 24 nm (Bi₂O₃-C1) and 10 ± 2.5 μm (Bi₂O₃-C2, Fig. 1c). Besides these mostly spherical particles, sheet-like materials of BiOBr (BiOBr-NS) and Bi₂O₂CO₃ (BOC-NS) were also prepared (Fig. 1d,e). SEM shows that the BiOBr nanosheets contain both stacks of sheets and “sand-rose”-oriented sheets. The Bi₂O₂CO₃ nanosheets are randomly oriented.

The crystal phases of the catalysts were determined by XRD (Fig. 2). Except for Bi₂O₃-C2, all Bi₂O₃ particles have the tetragonal β-Bi₂O₃ structure [42]. The Bi₂O₃-C2 sample comprises a monoclinic α-Bi₂O₃ phase as follows from the XRD pattern in Fig. 2 [43]. The crystal size of Bi₂O₃-NP calculated using the Scherrer equation (23 nm) agrees well with the size derived from TEM analysis. XRD confirms the formation of

Fig. 1. Characterization by TEM and SEM of the as-prepared catalysts. TEM images and size distribution of Bi₂O₃ NP (a). SEM images and size distributions of commercial Bi₂O₃-C1 and Bi₂O₃-C2 particles (b, c) and SEM images of BiOBr and Bi₂O₂CO₃ nanosheets (d,e).

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of the Bi₂O₃ NP, commercial Bi₂O₃ particles, BiOBr-NS and BOC-NS. The FSP synthesized nanoparticles and Bi₂O₃-C1 particles consist of the tetragonal β-Bi₂O₃ phase (JCPDS 01–078–1793), and the Bi₂O₃-C2 particles consist of the monoclinic α-Bi₂O₃ phase (JCPDS 01–076–1730) [43]. The nanosheets consist of BiOBr (JCPDS 01–078–0348) [44] and BOC-NS of Bi₂O₂CO₃ (JCPDS 01–070–8631) [47].

BiOBr nanosheets, which are characterized by diffraction lines corresponding to its (101), (102), (110) and (200) planes [44]. Besides BiOBr, a small amount of Bi-oxide hydroxide nitrate is observed (Fig. S1a) [19]. The formation of BOC-NS upon prolonged air exposure of the Bi₂O₃-NP is confirmed by the (101), (103), (110), and (114) diffraction lines, representing orthorhombic Bi₂O₂CO₃ [45–47]. The crystal structure and main morphological parameters of the catalysts are summarized in Table 1.

3.2. CO₂ Electroreduction

Based on the insight of Montiel et al. [45] that mass transport limitations of CO₂ during CO₂ER can substantially affect the morphology of Bi-oxide electrocatalysts, we investigated the different precursors in a GDE configuration. The electrocatalysts are spray painted on a GDL to obtain a GDE, which is placed in a flow cell to prevent CO₂ mass transport limitations (Fig. S3).

Fig. 3 shows the FE as a function of potential for the different catalyst precursors. All potentials are reported vs. Ag/AgCl. Except for the Bi₂O₃-

C2 catalyst, the Faradaic efficiencies and current densities follow the same trend. At –1.4 V, CO₂ electroreduction starts with traces of formate being detected, corresponding to an FE of 10–20% for the other catalysts. Upon increasing the potential to –1.6 V, the FE increases to 68% for the BiOBr-NS and Bi₂O₃-C1 catalysts and 77% for Bi₂O₃-NP and BOC-NS. The FE increases to 92% and 94%, respectively, at –2.2 V. The Faradaic balance is completed by forming H₂ and CO (Fig. S4). These Faradaic efficiencies are similar to those previously reported for Bi-based catalysts [8,9,11]. Thus, our findings confirm the high FE to formate in electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction for the Bi-based catalysts. Slight differences exist among the catalysts at potentials below –2.2 V, as the Bi₂O₃-NP and BOC-NS samples show a steeper increase in FE around –1.6 V and reach the maximum FE around –1.8 V. The α-Bi₂O₃-C2 sample displays the lowest performance regarding FE (~60%) and current density. This is most likely due to the very large size of the Bi₂O₃-C2 particles, corresponding to a very low surface area. We prepared another electrode with a higher loading of 1.7 mg/cm² Bi₂O₃-C2 particles, which increased FE and current density to 80% and 60 mA/cm² at –2.2 V (Fig. S4). Although improved, this performance is still the lowest among the catalysts investigated.

We employed XRD and electron microscopy to determine the crystal phase and morphology of the materials after CO₂ER. SEM images reveal that the morphology of all catalysts changed into sheets, except for the α-Bi₂O₃-C2 particles (Fig. 4). The sheets formed from the BiOBr-NS and Bi₂O₃-C1 precursors are quite similar, both in size and the rounded shape of the agglomerated sheets. Their sizes are significantly larger than the sheets obtained from the Bi₂O₃-NP and BOC-NS precursors. The α-Bi₂O₃-C2 particles largely maintained their original globular particle morphology (Fig. S5). Nevertheless, close inspection of the images

Table 1

Morphology of Bi-based electrocatalysts. The width of the nanosheets is used as an indicator of their size (Fig. S2).

Catalyst	Phase	Shape	Size
Bi ₂ O ₃ -NP	β-Bi ₂ O ₃	Spherical particle	23 ± 4.6 nm
Bi ₂ O ₃ -C1	β-Bi ₂ O ₃	Spherical particle	175 ± 24 nm
Bi ₂ O ₃ -C2	α-Bi ₂ O ₃	Particle	10 ± 2.5 μm
BiOBr-NS	BiOBr	Nanosheets	510 ± 165 nm
BOC-NS	Bi ₂ O ₂ CO ₃	Nanosheets	324 ± 89 nm

Fig. 3. Potential-dependent Faradaic efficiency and current density of potentiostatic CO₂ER experiments. CO₂ER was performed in a flow cell with 0.5 M KHCO₃ catholyte and 10 ml/min CO₂. The graphs plot the FE values (a) and current density (b) vs. the applied potential (V vs. Ag/AgCl). Every as-prepared electrode was subjected to 2 CVs between 0.4 V and the potential used for the subsequent 30 min chrono amperometry.

Fig. 4. Characterization by SEM after CO₂ER. SEM images of the Bi-based catalysts were obtained on a GDE after 30 min CO₂ER at -2.0 V in 0.5 M KHCO₃.

reveals that sheet-like material is present around these large particles, indicating that some dissolution and redeposition of Bi from the α -Bi₂O₃ occurred during CO₂ER. The differences in the formation of sheets is strongly dependent on the initial size of the Bi₂O₃ particles. The trend in the size of the sheets is related to the size of the Bi₂O₃ particles for initial sizes up to 200 nm. The use of micrometer sized particles with a very low surface area inhibits the conversion to sheets during these experiments. The observation of sheet formation in all materials is in line with various literature reports and can explain why comparable catalytic performance is observed [10,11].

The Pourbaix diagram of Bi shows that metallic Bi is thermodynamically the most stable phase at typical potentials needed to reduce CO₂ formate (< -0.6 V vs RHE) over the whole pH scale [48]. However,

the presence of CO₂ and carbonates leads to the formation of a Bi₂O₂CO₃ phase, which has been reported to remain present up to -1.6 V vs RHE [10,49]. Bi₂O₃ nanoparticles have been reported as CO₂ capture material, yielding Bi₂O₂CO₃. The Bi₂O₂CO₃ formation rate with dissolved CO₂ was found to be pH dependent, [49] being roughly 3 times higher at pH 9 than pH 5.5. In this work, a CO₂ saturated solution of 0.5 M KHCO₃ (pH 7.5) was used. Under these conditions, CO₂ (~ 33 mM), HCO₃⁻ (~ 0.5 M) as well as some CO₃²⁻ are present in the solution [50]. The conversion of Bi₂O₃ to Bi₂O₂CO₃ prior to electrochemical CO₂ reduction was also evaluated. After 3 min in CO₂-saturated KHCO₃ solution (a typical time between inserting the electrode in a KHCO₃ solution and starting an electrochemical experiment), the Bi₂O₃-NP were completely converted to Bi₂O₂CO₃ (Fig. S1b). Bi₂O₃-C1 was only partially converted

to Bi₂O₂CO₃. Therefore, it can be concluded that the conversion to Bi₂O₂CO₃ occurs in a very short time in a CO₂-saturated KHCO₃ solution at pH 7.5 and the conversion rate depends on the particle size. From these findings, we infer that the Bi₂O₃ precursors are (partially) converted to Bi₂O₂CO₃ prior to the application of a reduction potential. The instability of Bi₂O₃ and formation of Bi₂O₂CO₃ from Bi-based materials in contact with CO₂ has also been observed in photocatalytic studies [51, 52]. During electrochemical CO₂ reduction, the local pH near the electrodes can increase due to the formation of OH⁻ for during the electrochemical reduction of CO₂ to formate [53]. This can increase the local concentration of CO₃²⁻ due to the reaction of the in situ generated OH⁻ with the high concentration of CO₂ flowing through the GDE [50,53]. This can increase the rate of Bi₂O₂CO₃ formation and stabilize this phase at negative potentials [49]. After CO₂ER the catalyst phases are analyzed by XRD. The bulk phase of all catalysts includes the Bi₂O₂CO₃ phase after CO₂ER at -1.4 V (Fig. 5). Bi₂O₂CO₃ is the dominant phase in Bi₂O₃-NP. A small contribution of metallic Bi is observed as follows from the (012) diffraction line in the XRD pattern. Bi₂O₂CO₃ remains the dominant phase up to a potential of -2.0 V. The narrowing of the (103) diffraction line indicates the growth of the Bi₂O₂CO₃ crystal domains

from 14 nm to 31 nm when increasing the potential from -1.4 V to -2.0 V (Fig. S9). BOC-NS are mainly made up of the Bi₂O₂CO₃ phase up to a potential of -1.8 V. Although, for instance BOC-NS contains more metallic Bi than Bi₂O₃-NP, the data do not allow to conclude on a systematic trend of the amount and size of the metallic Bi phase (Fig. 5). The XRD patterns are similar to those presented by Montiel et al., demonstrating the persistence of the Bi₂O₂CO₃ phase beyond the thermodynamic reduction potential of Bi³⁺ [10]. On the contrary, the larger sheets formed from BiOBr-NS and Bi₂O₃-C1 are reduced to metallic Bi at a potential of -1.6 V [9]. TEM analysis confirms the metallic nature of the sheets (Fig. S10, S11) and agrees well with the literature [7,9,12,44]. The initial particle size affects the evolution of the active phase. While the relatively large Bi₂O₃-C1 particle reduction results in metallic Bi without Bi₂O₂CO₃, the smaller particles in Bi₂O₃-NP form a stable Bi₂O₂CO₃ phase. From this, we infer that a high dispersion of Bi-oxide precursor results in rapid transformation into Bi₂O₂CO₃ sheets prior to and during CO₂ER, which are most likely stable against reduction to Bi metal because of the presence of CO₂ and carbonates in the solution. However, when the surface area of Bi-oxide is low, Bi-oxide dissolution and reactions with CO₂ or carbonates that would lead to Bi₂O₂CO₃ are

Fig. 5. XRD analysis after CO₂ER. XRD patterns of the Bi₂O₃ nanoparticles, Bi₂O₃-C1 particles, BiOBr-NS, and BOC-NS were recorded after 2 CV's and 30 min of CO₂ER at potentials from -1.4 to -2.2 V vs Ag/AgCl, (metallic Bi identified according to JCPDS 00-005-0519) [9].

hampered. This favors the direct conversion of Bi-oxide to metallic Bi. An exception is α -Bi₂O₃-C2, which is almost entirely reduced to metallic Bi at -1.4 V with only a minor contribution of Bi₂O₂CO₃ (Fig. S6). This suggests that contrary to β -Bi₂O₃, the α -Bi₂O₃ phase does not readily convert to Bi-subcarbonate. Bi₂O₂CO₃ consists of Bi₂O₂²⁺ layers with carbonate ions in between the layers. The atomic arrangement of Bi₂O₂²⁺ is also a structural element of the β -Bi₂O₃. However, the monoclinic α -Bi₂O₃ phase does not have this structural element of Bi₂O₂²⁺ layers and was found thermodynamically more stable than the metastable β -Bi₂O₃ and Bi₂O₂CO₃ phases [46,54]. Combined with our observations, we presume that α -Bi₂O₃ does not enable CO₂ insertion by segregation into Bi₂O₂²⁺ layers before reducing to metallic Bi. As the Bi metal particles obtained from α -Bi₂O₃-C2 retain the shape of the precursor, we can infer that these particles are reduced to metallic Bi without forming intermediate sheets. Moreover, the dissolution of Bi from the α -Bi₂O₃ phase is too slow to form a layered Bi₂O₂CO₃, and only a small amount of sheets are observed around the particles. Nevertheless, due to the significantly larger size of Bi₂O₃-C2, we cannot exclude a more pronounced surface area effect already observed with intermediate-sized Bi₂O₃-C1.

Our findings indicate that the initial morphology only indirectly impacts the FE and current density. The Bi₂O₃ NP, Bi₂O₃-C1, and the BiOBr-NS and BOC-NS sheet materials all reach similar activity at a potential of -2.2 V. The presence of the Bi₂O₂CO₃ phase coincides with the slightly higher FE observed for the Bi₂O₃ NP and Bi₂O₂CO₃ catalyst between -1.4 and -1.8 V and agree with the results of Montiel et al. [10]. Nevertheless, the differences in FE are only marginally more significant than the standard deviation. Despite the almost identical shape and activity of the catalysts, the bulk phases differ significantly. Conversion of Bi₂O₃ to Bi₂O₂CO₃ rapidly occurs unless a low surface area of the material hampers dissolution and CO₂ insertion. Then, direct transformation to the metal is observed.

The surface composition of the Bi₂O₃-NP and BiOBr-NS was characterized by quasi-in situ XPS after CO₂ER at -2.2 V vs Ag/AgCl. After the electrochemical reaction, the sample was removed from the electrolyte and dried in a controlled and oxygen-free environment before transfer to the analysis chamber. This procedure prevents reoxidation of reduced surface species by avoiding transfer through the air. The Bi 4f_{7/2} binding energies of 158.2 and 159.2 eV for the Bi₂O₃-NP and BiOBr-NS precursors indicate that Bi is in the +3 oxidation state (Fig. 6) [55].

After CO₂ER, a metallic contribution at a Bi 4f_{7/2} binding energy of 156.9 eV is present in the spectra for both catalysts. The reduction of Bi-oxide is not complete as a feature at a Bi 4f_{7/2} binding energy of 159.3 eV remains for Bi₂O₃-NP and at 159.0 eV for BiOBr-NS. Inspection of the Br 3p and 3d regions of BiOBr-NS before and after CO₂ER demonstrates the absence of bromide after CO₂ER, excluding a BiOBr phase (Fig. S14). As we can also exclude reoxidation of metallic Bi to Bi₂O₃, it is most likely that the oxide phase in the BiOBr-NS sample after CO₂ER is Bi₂O₂CO₃. These Bi 4f_{7/2} binding energies are closest to that of a reference Bi₂O₂CO₃ sample (158.7 eV) and higher than the binding energy for Bi₂O₃ (158.3 eV) (Fig. S13). The slightly higher binding energies in Figure compared to reference Bi₂O₂CO₃ (Fig. S13) are most likely caused by surface charging due to the absence of charge compensation in the NAP-XPS instrument. As such, it is likely that the oxide phase observed in Bi₂O₃-NP after CO₂ER can also be assigned to Bi₂O₂CO₃. Nevertheless, due to possible charging, we cannot completely exclude that this sample contains some remaining Bi₂O₃.

In line with the XRD results, surface analysis by XPS suggests that a Bi₂O₂CO₃ contribution persists during CO₂ER on the Bi₂O₃-NP sample. Moreover, XPS analysis of the BiOBr-NS sample suggests some Bi₂O₂CO₃, not visible by XRD, could also be present during CO₂ER on the surface of the reduced BiOBr-NS. Lü et al. proposed that Bi₂O₂CO₃ is formed during CO₂ER due to the chemisorption of CO₂. [16]. This would offer a reasonable explanation for the comparable electrochemical performance of most of our Bi-based catalysts during potentiostatic measurements (Fig. 3).

3.2.1. Catalyst comparison at industrially relevant conditions

For practical implementation of electrochemical CO₂ reduction, the current density must surpass at least 100 mA/cm², [56,57] with stability requirements in the order of thousands of hours [58,59]. High current densities and prolonged reduction will likely affect the catalyst phase, forming metallic Bi. [26] To compare the catalyst under industrially relevant conditions during prolonged CO₂ER conditions, the Faradaic efficiency of the catalysts is compared over 6 h CO₂ER at a current density of 200 mA/cm² (Fig. 7a). The potentials required to obtain this current density are roughly 1 V more negative than the potentials used in the potentiostatic measurements (Fig. S7). The FE of the BiOBr-NS, BOC-NS, and Bi₂O₃-C1 decreased from $\sim 90\%$ after 1 h to 83% after

Fig. 6. Quasi-in situ XPS analysis of the Bi₂O₃-NP and BiOBr-NS after 2CVs and CO₂ER at -2.2 V vs Ag/AgCl. (a) Bi 4f core-line region of the Bi₂O₃-NP precursor (bottom, purple) and electrode after (top) CO₂ER. (b) Bi 4f core-line region of the BiOBr-NS precursor (bottom, red) and electrode after (top) CO₂ER. The oxidation state after CO₂ER of metallic Bi and oxidized Bi are indicated in blue and yellow, respectively.

Fig. 7. Galvanostatic CO₂ER experiments. (a) FE as a function of time of the catalysts at 200 mA/cm² in 0.5 M KHCO₃. Circles indicate the FE towards formate, squares to hydrogen, and diamonds to CO. (b) XRD diffractograms after 6 h CO₂ER at 200 mA/cm².

6 h CO₂ER. The Bi₂O₃-NP sample, on the other hand, maintains a high FE above 90% during 6 h CO₂ER, close to the FE observed at lower potentials (Fig. 3).

SEM imaging reveals further changes in the morphology after prolonged CO₂ER under these conditions. Fig. 8a-d shows the as-prepared GDEs based on the Bi₂O₃-NP, BiOBr-NS, Bi₂O₃-C1, and BOC-NS catalysts. The Bi₂O₃-NP, BiOBr-NS, and BOC-NS particles fully cover the surface of the GDL. As the particles of Bi₂O₃-C1 are relatively large, they do not entirely cover the surface of the GDL. Fig. 8e-h shows the GDEs after CO₂ER for 6 h at 200 mA/cm². The amount of sheets in the samples used in prolonged CO₂ER at high current density is substantially lower than after the potentiostatic measurements (Fig. 4). No sheets remain during experiments with Bi₂O₃-NP and BiOBr-NS. In contrast, only a few sheets are observed in used BOC-NS. The Bi₂O₃-C1 sample with the largest particles shows the most well-defined sheet morphology after 6 h CO₂ER. As the Bi₂O₃-NP reaches a higher FE, we conclude that the sheet-like morphology of the catalyst does not necessarily lead to the highest FE at these conditions.

XRD analysis reveals that the main phase in the used catalysts is

metallic Bi, implying that the Bi₂O₂CO₃ phase observed for Bi₂O₃-NP at lower potentials is not stable at these conditions (Fig. 7). Despite the reduction of the Bi₂O₃-NP to metallic Bi, a high FE of ~92% is maintained, which is higher than that of the other catalysts (~85%) at these conditions. The Bi₂O₃-NP is the only catalyst for which the FE does not decrease when a more negative potential is applied. As such, these data indicate that a high FE is not dependent on the presence of bulk Bi₂O₂CO₃, as might be taken from the findings of our potentiostatic investigations and observations made by Montiel et al. [10]. Metallic Bi catalysts can maintain high activity towards CO₂ER under industrially relevant conditions. CO₂ reduction does not necessarily proceed via the same reaction mechanism for metallic Bi as for Bi₂O₂CO₃. Around -3 V vs Ag/AgCl, proton-assisted CO₂ reduction to formate and stepwise CO₂ reduction via the CO₂ anion to formate can occur [60]. A high FE is then mainly governed by Bi's poor hydrogen evolution characteristics. Galvanostatic measurements at fixed total current imply a lower current density on smaller particle sizes. A lower current density requires a lower potential (Fig. S7), decreasing the rate of the hydrogen evolution reaction. This could explain the slightly higher FE observed on the

Fig. 8. Characterization by SEM after galvanostatic CO₂ER. SEM images of the GDE covered with catalyst particles before (a-d) and after (e-h) 6 h CO₂ER at 200 mA/cm² were obtained.

Bi₂O₃-NP (Fig. 7).

4. Conclusions

Bi-based electrocatalysts undergo substantial morphological transformations during CO₂ electroreduction to formate. Therefore, varying the Bi precursor to the electrocatalyst has only a marginal impact on the FE to formate during potentiostatic measurements. At -1.6 V vs Ag/AgCl, β -Bi₂O₃ nanoparticles (23 nm) and Bi₂O₂CO₃ nanosheets exhibit a FE nearly 10% higher than BiOBr nanosheets and larger β -Bi₂O₃ particles (175 nm). At a more negative potential of -2.2 V, such differences mostly disappear, with the materials reaching an FE of $93 \pm 2\%$. During the electrochemical reduction of CO₂, all the Bi catalyst precursors change rapidly into predominantly nanosheets, likely related to the formation of Bi₂O₂CO₃. The sheets formed from the BiOBr-NS and Bi₂O₃-C1 precursors are significantly larger than those obtained from Bi₂O₃-NP and BOC-NS precursors. Only the use of large α -Bi₂O₃ particles inhibits the transformation into sheets. The instability of Bi₂O₃ precursors is most likely due to the dissolution of Bi-oxide ions and the formation of layered Bi₂O₂CO₃ phase with CO₂ in the electrolyte. Depending on the potential and the stabilization by CO₂, reduction of this layered phase can result in metallic Bi that retains some of the layered morphology of its precursor as suggested by XRD and SEM. The size of the precursor has a strong influence on the active phase formed during the electrochemical CO₂ reduction reaction. Starting from Bi-oxide nanoparticle precursor and in a cell configuration conducive to a fast supply of CO₂, the layered Bi₂O₂CO₃ phase forms and remains stable with negligible formation of Bi metal, even beyond the thermodynamic reduction potential, up to a potential of -2.2 V vs. Ag/AgCl. BiOBr-NS and larger β -Bi₂O₃ particle precursors readily reduce to metallic Bi at potentials more negative than -1.4 vs Ag/AgCl. At high surface area, Bi-oxide dissolution and reprecipitation as Bi₂O₂CO₃ is favored over direct reduction to metallic Bi. Conversely, there is a tendency for large particles to convert to Bi metal directly. The persistence of the Bi₂O₂CO₃ phase can explain the slightly higher FE observed for the Bi₂O₃ nanoparticles and BOC-NS catalysts. Quasi-in situ XPS analysis of samples used during electrochemical CO₂ reduction suggests that the surface may still contain oxidized Bi. Therefore, this surface oxide may be the active phase, even for the catalysts reduced to metallic Bi, which can explain the minor performance differences between the catalysts. When the electrochemical CO₂ reduction is carried out at industrially relevant conditions, i.e., at a high current density and more negative potential, complete reduction of Bi-oxide to the metal is observed in all precursors. In this case, the significant driving force for Bi reduction prevents the morphological changes into sheets observed at less negative potentials. Nonetheless, a constant high FE of $\sim 92\%$ for the Bi₂O₃-NP catalyst was achieved at 200 mA/cm² during 6 h CO₂ER. The higher FE of the FSP synthesized Bi₂O₃-NP compared to larger-sized catalyst precursors is assigned to the increased surface area of the nanosized catalyst.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tim Wissink: Conceptualization, Investigation, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Alex J.W. Man:** Investigation, Validation. **Jason M.J.J. Heinrichs** and **Rim C.J. van de Poll:** TEM imaging. **Marta C. Figueiredo:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Emiel J.M. Hensen:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interest or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work in this paper.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jcou.2023.102604](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2023.102604).

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